

AUTO MANUFACTURERS INDUSTRY IN INDIA

Meghana S Bhandari & Megha K. S.

First year MBA, College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, India.

Email: meghanabhandari3011@gmail.com & meghaks456@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The auto manufacturers industry is one of the most important drivers of economic growth of India and one with high participation in global value chains. The growth of this sector has been on the back of strong government support which has helped it carve a unique path among the manufacturing sectors of India. The auto manufacturers produced in the country uniquely cater to the demands of low- and middle-income groups of population which makes this sector stand out among the other auto manufacturers-producing countries.

This paper analyzes the roles of government policy, infrastructure, and other enabling factors in the expansion of the auto manufacturers and automotive component sectors of India. In 2017, India became the world's fourth largest auto manufacturers market, and the demand for Indian vehicles continues to grow in the domestic and international markets.

To meet the future needs of customers (including the electrical vehicles) and stay ahead of competition, manufacturers are now catching up on upgradation, digitization, and automation. This paper also analyzes India's national policy in light of these developments.

Keywords: Auto manufacturers industries, SWOT analysis, Decision factors, Development strategies in auto manufacturers.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The automobile industry is an important driver of the economic growth in India and one of the successful sectors in which the country has high participation in global value chains (GVCs). This chapter analyzes the role of government policy, infrastructure, and other enabling factors in the expansion of the automobile and automotive component sectors and the direction they are likely to take for growth path in the next few years. The analysis in this chapter is organized into seven sections: The first section discusses the structure and makeup of the Indian automobile industry. The second section analyzes the growth of the sector over the past decades, while the third section discusses the role of government. The fourth section deals with other enabling factors in the growth of the industry. The fifth section analyzes initiatives in upgrading and innovation. The sixth section includes a discussion of the future scenario and the seventh section concludes.

2. OBJECTIVES:

1. To know about the Indian Automobile Industry.
2. To study the role of Indian Automobile Industry in the country's growth.
3. To know the initiatives of the Government towards and the achievement by the Indian Automobile Industries.
4. To know the dimensions of customer satisfaction towards Indian Automobile Industries.

5. To understand the reasons behind slowdown and downfall of the Indian Automobile Industry.
6. To understand requirements of the consumer from the automobile industry.

3.METHODOLOGY:

The information presented and analyzed are primarily based on secondary data gathered from various online sources such as websites, internet blogs, books, journals, discussions, and articles

4.OVERVIEW OF AUTOMANUFACTURE INDUSRTY IN INDIA:

Today rules and regulations had been changed in favorable the automobile industry the first reason for this knowledge about new technologies spreads quickly to different parts of the country. Another reason is that ability to attract customers and tools to apply knowledge at the disposal of individual income and organizations expenditures. Particularly in the automobile market survey result the sale of passenger car have increased by three folds than what it used to be five years down the line. The emerge as the destination of choice in the world for design and manufacture of automobiles and auto components with output reaching a level of US\$ 145 billion accounting for more than 10% of the GDP and providing additional employment to 25 million of people by 2016. The Government of India takes necessary steps not only to maintain the high rate of growth but also retain the attractive of Indian market for further attractive the competitive strength of Indian companies. The Government was setup through the development council on automobile and allied industries, constituted a task force to draw up a decade mission plan for Indian automotive industry, the challenge was to give a shape of innovative plan of action with full participation of stakeholders and to complexity it into a mission mode to remove barrier coming in the way of growth industry. Automobile industry to meet the customer demands and changing business needs, they raise a strategy to accomplish the demands of consumers as well as face the competitor's challenge with the aid of new technology and innovative ideas. The industry service to the society next advance stage introduction of new electric cars in the place of LPG, petrol and diesel cars due to continuous hiking of fuel prices as well as to reduce the emission of carbon-dioxide in the earth. The focus of the research enhances the passenger car segments and how to develop with sophisticated technologies is used in production of cars; sales of vehicles in the particular segment, revenue generation etc. and create millions of employment opportunities both direct as well as indirect nature for rural and urban areas in this sector. There are various reasons for the growth of the Indian automobile market such as: The people have more disposable income as economy is growing. Increase in the need of mobility due to urbanization and leisure travel. Car finance options available from Financial Institutes at reasonable rate of interest and length of repayment. Availability of service centers, spare parts across the nation in near locality. Improvement in highway infrastructure and reduce cost of service and time.

5. AUTO MANUFACTURES INDUATRIES TYPES

Introduction Stage

The introduction stage is when a car tries to "get noticed" and distinguish itself among the

crowd. Marketing moves include an advertising campaign, sales promotions and word-of-mouth spread through social media. An early adopter whose persona complements the car is almost too much to ask for, but it would be the brass ring at this stage.

Example: Self-driving cars

Growth Stage

The growth stage is when profits grow commensurate with public visibility. Marketing moves include continuing those efforts that fired on all cylinders in the first stage and abandoning those that failed to resonate with consumers. This is a hands-on marketing stage where the need to pivot quickly is vital.

Example: Tesla Model S

Maturity Stage

The maturity stage occurs when a product reaches market saturation, and competition can be intense. This is usually the longest of the four stages. Marketing moves include virtually any change to the four P's of marketing: product, place, price and promotion. The manufacturer may roll out new features to the product to lure a new target audience. It may broaden distribution channels, raise or lower prices, and probably redouble promotional initiatives.

Example: Ford Focus

Decline Stage

The decline stage is when profitability suffers to the point that keeping the production line open can no longer be justified. Marketing moves are minimal unless the car is a sentimental favorite among consumers, in which case some type of farewell tour may be staged.

Example: Diesel cars

Vehicle life cycle

6. TOP 10 AUTO MANUFACTURES INDUSTRY TRENDS AND INNOVATIONS IN 2021:

The below figure shows the top 10 auto manufactures industries innovations and trends in 2021. auto manufactures Industries Identifies new opportunities and emerging technologies for gaining an advantage. As a result of technological advancements, the efficiency of workers and operations are increased and costs are reduced. Big Data, Robotics and Artificial Intelligence will transform these industries. The COVID-19 outbreak has forced many businesses to reconsider their workplace and environmental policies. AI and IoT technologies improves processes in the Oil and Gas Industries. Inspection of both onshore and offshore equipment are done using drones and predictive maintenance.

The below chart shows India’s Vehicle production
Two-wheelers, including motorcycles, scooters and mopeds, account for most production in India’s growing automobile market, giving consumers in the world’s second-largest developing economy more affordable options for transportation than passenger vehicles.

The below figure shows the top 10 trends in auto manufactures Industry.

7. SWOC ANALYSIS:

Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Challenges (SWOC) analysis is a method of determining a company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges. Auto manufactures Industries will be able to map the present business environment and identify internal strategic aspects such as strengths and weaknesses, as well as external strategic factors such as opportunities and challenges, using this technique. Here we discuss in detail the Strength, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Challenges of the auto manufactures industries.

7.1Strength: -

- Investment by foreign car manufacturers.
- Increase in the export levels.
- Low cost and cheap labor.
- Rise in the working- and middle-class income.
- Increasing demand for European quality.
- Expert skills in producing small cars-good for environment.
- Large pool of engineers.

7.2Opportunity: -

- Growing population in the country.
- Focus from the government in improving the road Infrastructure.
- Rising living standards.
- Increase in income level.
- Better car technology is demanded.
- Rising rural demand.
- The car is a status symbol.

- Women drivers have increased.

7.3 Weakness: -

- Low quality compared to other automotive countries.
- Low labor productivity.
- High interest rate and overhead level.
- Production cost are generally higher than some other Asian states, such as China.
- Low investment in R&D area.
- Local demand is still towards low-cost vehicles, or to low-income level.

7.4 Threats: -

- Less skilled labor.
- Lack of technologies for Indian companies.
- Increase in the import tariff and technology cost.
- Imports of two-wheeler from the Chinese market in India.
- Smaller players that do not fulfill international standards.
- Increased congestion in the Urban areas

8. TOP 10 AUTO MANUFACTURES INDUSTRIES :

The below figure shows the list of India's Auto Manufactures company.

8.1 Tata Motors Ltd

Tata Motors is **one of the leading Automobile Companies in India** and the world, providing mobility solutions to **over 175 countries**. The portfolio includes a **wide range of cars, utility vehicles, trucks, and buses**. The company is the largest automobile company in the list Top 10 Automobile Companies in India based on the Turnover The Company has a **strong global network of 134 subsidiaries**, associate companies and joint ventures, including the Jaguar Land Rover in the UK and the Tata Daewoo in South Korea. TML offers automotive products, ranging from sub-one-tonne to 49-tonne Gross Vehicle Weight (GVW) trucks, small, medium, and large buses and coaches and passenger vehicles.

8.2. Maruti Suzuki India Ltd

Market leader in the passenger vehicle segment in India. The Company was **established in 1981**. A joint venture agreement was signed between the Government of India and Suzuki Motor Corporation (SMC), Japan in 1982. The Company became a subsidiary of SMC in 2002. **Maruti is the Second Largest Automobile Companies in India by the Revenue** In terms of production volume and sales, the Company is now **SMC's largest subsidiary**. **SMC currently holds 56.21% of its equity stake**. Maruti Suzuki largest car company in India based on Market share .The Company has two state-of-the-art manufacturing facilities located in Gurugram and Manesar in Haryana, with a combined **annual production capacity of ~1.58 million units per annum**.

8.3. Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd

Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd., a **mobility products and farm solutions** provider, is the flagship company of the Mahindra Group. It is one of the leading car company in India. Since assembling the **first vehicle in 1947**, The Company has grown rapidly. It is the **Third Largest Automobile Companies in India by Total Sales**. Today, The Company offers a wide range of products and solutions ranging from **SUVs to electric vehicles, pickups, commercial vehicles, tractors, two-wheelers, and construction equipment**. It is one of the leading Indian automobile companies.

8.4. Hero MotoCorp Ltd

World's **largest two-wheeler manufacturer in 2001**, in terms of unit volume sales in a calendar year, and has maintained the coveted title for the **past 18 consecutive years**. With over 90 million satisfied customers across the globe, it continues to champion socio-economic progress and empowerment through its range of products and services .It became the **only Indian two-wheeler company** to set up a manufacturing base in Latin America when it started operations at its manufacturing facility in Colombia in 2016. The company is a part of Hero group.Hero MotoCorp currently has an **annual combined production capacity of around 9 million units of two-wheelers**. The is the fourth largest automobile company among the Top 10 automobile manufacturing companies in India.

8.5. Bajaj Auto Ltd

Present in **over 70 nations**, Bajaj Auto is the world's **3rd largest manufacturer of motorcycles and the largest manufacturer of three-wheelers**. Its footprint stretches over a wide range of industries, spanning automobiles (two-wheelers manufacturer and three-wheelers manufacturer). The company is a part of Bajaj Group .Bajaj Auto is ranked as **the world's fourth-largest three and two-wheeler manufacturer** and the Bajaj brand is well-known across several countries in Latin America, Africa, Middle East, South, and Southeast Asia. The company is fifth in the list of Top 10 automobile manufacturing companies in India. Bajaj Auto International Holdings BV is a **100% Netherlands based subsidiary** of Bajaj Auto Ltd. Over the years, through this subsidiary, Bajaj Auto has invested a total of €198.1 million (H 1,219 crore) and holds approximately **48% stake in KTM AG of Austria (KTM), the fastest-growing motorcycle brand in the world**.

8.6. Ashok Leyland Ltd

Ashok Leyland, **the flagship of the Hinduja group**, is the **2nd largest manufacturer of commercial vehicles in India, the 4th largest manufacturer of buses in the world, and the 10th largest manufacturers of trucks** .Headquartered in Chennai, 9 manufacturing plants give an international footprint – 7 in India, a bus manufacturing facility in Ras Al Khaimah (UAE). Ashok Leyland has a well-diversified portfolio across the automobile industry. Ashok Leyland has recently been **ranked as the 38th best brand in India** .Ashok Leyland has a product range from **2.5T GVW (Gross Vehicle Weight) to 49T GTW (Gross Trailer Weight) in trucks, 16 to 80 seater buses**, vehicles for defences and special applications, and diesel engines for industrial, genset and marine applications .**Ashok Leyland launched India's first electric bus and Euro 6 compliant truck in 2016**. Over millions of passengers use Ashok Leyland buses to get to their destinations every day and 7,00,000 trucks keep the wheels of the economy moving.

8.7. TVS Motor Company Ltd

TVS Motor Company is the **third-largest two-wheeler manufacturer in India**, with revenue of 15129 Cr INR (2017-18). The company has an annual production capacity of 4 million 2 wheelers & 120,000 3 wheelers. TVS Group spans across industries like **Automobile, Aviation, Education, Electronics, Energy, Finance, Housing, Insurance, Investment, Logistics, Service and Textiles**. Has over 90 Companies under the umbrella. The company has **four manufacturing plants, three located in India** (Hosur in Tamil Nadu, Mysore in Karnataka and Nalagarh in Himachal Pradesh) and one in Indonesia at Karawang. The company is among the Top 10 Automobile Companies in India.

8.8. Eicher Motors Ltd

Eicher Motors Limited (EML) (Bloomberg: EIM IN Reuters: EICH.NS) is the **listed parent of Royal Enfield, the global leader in middleweight motorcycles.** The **world’s oldest motorcycle brand** in continuous production, Royal Enfield has made its distinctive motorcycles **since 1901.** With modern development facilities in **Leicestershire, UK and Chennai, India,** Royal Enfield makes its motorcycles in Tamil Nadu for the world. In addition to motorcycles, Eicher has a **joint venture with Sweden’s AB Volvo – Volvo Eicher Commercial Vehicles Limited (VECV)** – which is driving modernization in India’s commercial vehicle space, and in other developing countries.

8.9. Force Motors Ltd

Force Motors was **established in 1958** by Shri. N. K. Firodia, with the vision to provide affordable commercial transport for the masses by harnessing the best available technology and offering economical, reliable and efficient products. The company is 9th in the list of Top 10 Automobile Companies in India. Today, its range includes **Small Commercial Vehicles (SCV), Multi-Utility Vehicles (MUV), Light Commercial Vehicles (LCV), Special Utility Vehicles (SUV) and Agricultural Tractors.** So, no matter what the need be, Force has a solution to offer.

8.10. SML ISUZU Ltd

SML Isuzu Ltd. (SMLI) is a **trusted and reliable commercial vehicle manufacturer since 1985.** It has over 33 Years of experience in producing **Light & Medium commercial vehicles** to meet Indian customer needs. SMIL is the first company to manufacture and supply state of the artfully built Buses, Ambulances, and customized vehicles. It is the last in the list of top Automobile Companies in India Sumitomo Corporation, Japan and Isuzu Motors, Japan respectively **hold 44% and 15%** shareholding in the Company. It is among the list of Top 10 Automobile Companies in India.

The below chart shows the top auto manufactures industries revenue

9. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY:

The automobile sector in India is the sixth-largest in the world. The country's share in the automobile industry is set to increase further considering the rising population, rising incomes of people and their need for private transport vehicles. With an increase in their stakes in the Indian market, the CSR investments of auto industry players are also increasing in the country. In this context, let us look at five automobile companies in India that take CSR seriously.

Tata Motors

Tata Motors is one brand that takes CSR very seriously. According to its Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Report for FY 2019-20, the company made a social investment of Rs. 25.19 crore in the last Financial Year, of which 22.91 crores were toward CSR Programmed & Projects, drinking water projects that are mainstreamed in CSR agenda and one-time investment towards disaster response. A major portion of funds was spent on the CSR programmed which are deployed in the project mode and are part of our Common Minimum Programmed (CMP) and Location-Specific Programmed (LSP).

Maruti Suzuki Maruti Suzuki has been increasing its CSR expenditure year on year. It solidifies its commitment to CSR by spending almost always, a higher amount than prescribed. For example, in 2019-20, the company spent its full budget of Rs. 168.2 crores on social initiatives.

Maruti Suzuki utilizes a major chunk of its CSR energies to road safety since there isn't much awareness about it in the consciousness of an average Indian. Pedestrians and drivers in the country are known to flout traffic rules in every small town or large metro. To address this, the company has set up driving schools across the country in collaboration with its dealers to impart quality driving training. The company has executed this with the involvement of state governments and the local administration in road safety awareness, thus reducing the number of road accidents and law enforcement.

Hero Moto Corp

Hero Moto Corp has been spending more than the prescribed amount for its CSR initiatives for the last four subsequent financial years. In FY 2019-20, the company spent Rs. 130.61 crores on CSR initiatives.

Bajaj Auto

Bajaj auto all of its stakeholders into account in its CSR policy. It is of prime importance for the company to ensure care of human and environmental rights while being ethical. Therefore, the company's CSR initiatives revolve around the motto – Growth with Mother Nature's blessings. The company implements its CSR initiatives through NGOs and charitable agencies. Apart from the non-profit sector, the local authorities and civil society groups are also roped in where required for the implementation of certain CSR projects.

Eicher Motors

Eicher Motors spent about Rs. 55.39 crores for its CSR projects in FY 2019-20. The company has set up a Good earth Education Foundation, to implement its mission: "To educate India's children with a special emphasis on the girl child starting with primary education for the rural poor."

The below chart shows the CSR spent in Maruthi Suzuki

10. COVID-19 IMPACT:

- The BMW group has reported as on Aug 2020 its first quarterly operating loss since 2009.
- Toyota Motor reported as on Aug 2020 its smallest quarterly profit in last nine years as the covid-19 pandemic halved its car sales .
- UK light commercial vehicle reported as on Aug 2020 ,a slight increase in registrations since January .
- Honda Motors announced that the spread of corona virus disease 2019 has caused the global economic slow down and also affected Honda’s financial results.
- New Zealand’s Motor Industry Association said that the year is heavily affected by the covid-19 pandemic .
- Ford quarter 2 financial result were battered by the pandemic .
- Aston Martin has reported a widening operating loss for the first half of the year .
- Mitsubishi Motors has forecasted its second straight year losses due to fall in sales in part by the coronavirus pandemic.
- Hyundai motors affiliate KIA motors global vehicle sales fell heavily ,as the COVID-19 pandemic impacted auto demand around the world.
- Volkswagen group luxury car unit AUDI expects car sales to reach pre covid-19 levels only by 2022 or 2023. The COVID 19 pandemic has pushed global economy into a crisis not since 100 years .

Indian government has taken sincere efforts to curb this pandemic ,and has enforced a national lockdown. While the lockdown has helped limit spread of the virus ,it has severely affected the economy ,disrupting entire value chains of most major industries in India. The automotive

industry is among them ,who got severely affected .The auto mobile sector was already going through a slowdown over the last couple of years due structural changes starting with GST ,axle-load reforms ,Bharat stage -IV (BS-IV) to Bharat stage – VI (BS -VI) transition and so on . The COVID-19 lockdown has had a multiplier effect . A sustained stoppage of consumer demand due to lockdown is seen significantly affecting automobile industry revenues. The covid 19 pandemic has had a swift and severe impact on the global automobile industry .Not a day passes by without an automaker either suspending operations or operating with minimal workforce to keep coronavirus at bay . Symptoms include a disruption in Chinese parts export ,large scale manufacturing interruptions across Europe ,and the closure of assembly parts in the United states . This is placing intense pressure on automobile industry which is already coping with a down shift in global demand ,and likely leading to increased merger and acquisition activity

11. RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS:

Recommendation and suggestion of auto manufactures industry: - The Automobile companies must improve their process and should be efficient in order to implement their strategies quicker than competitors in times of economic downturns The National level Automotive Institute for training on automobile at International Training Institutes (ITIs) and Automotive Training Institute (ATIs) have to be set up. The Government of India should promote manufacturing and encourage exports of small cars, multi-utility vehicles, two and three wheelers, tractors and components which infuse necessary foreign currencies to India. Specific measures should be taken for expansion of domestic market. Government should hike its spending to create more jobs and boost the manufacturing sectors in the country. The Automobile companies should use their core competencies to overcome turbulent economic times. The Strategic alliance or acquisitions of Automobile companies encourage the morale of those lost markets and help them to experience a new life in a given bridge of time through collective efforts. The reason for acquiring the businesses is seen as a dependable strategy by the companies in a period of economic downturn. Advertising is an important factor for the Automobile companies to overcome economic downturns as it helps the affected companies to showcase their products in the market. The Automobile companies have to come out with new innovative products to attain advantage over their competition in the market. They must do it on priority and development of the most promising products should meet the immediate needs of their customers. The Automobile companies have to re-evaluate the marketing plan and business strategies as and when needed.

12. CONCLUSION:

India has been an attractive investment destination for global automobile and component manufacturers since the last two decades. Its growth story has been dominated by more homegrown lead firms. However, absorption of global best practices has been slower than in China. Strategies of firms in the Chinese auto industry provided a boost to technological learning more quickly and broadly than in India. Capable of end-to-end production, India has also become an assembly hub for large cars and manufacturing hub for small cars. Firms have started exporting to other countries. India-based manufacturers are engaged in global innovation networks and sourcing suitable technologies from all over the world to complement their own

R&D efforts.

13. REFERENCES:

[1] https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-13-8102-7_19 Introduction

[2]

<https://www.google.com/search?q=life+stage+of+automobile+&tbm=isch&ved=2ahUKEwj08>

[3]

<https://www.google.com/search?q=CSR+spent+by+auto+manufactures+in+india&tbm=isch&ved=2ahUKEwjP-Z74m8v3AhUtgWMGHWfTADgQ2->

[4] <https://www.inventiva.co.in/trends/10-automobile-companies/>